

PROGRESSIVE APPROACHES TO RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. The article discusses the basic principles of the system-activity approach. In practice, various types and techniques of work in this technology are offered....

Key words: Russian language, innovative training, lesson, student, educational process, distance learning, innovative approach.

Innovative approaches to teaching the Russian language are associated primarily with changing the role of the teacher. In modern conditions, it is very important that the teacher does not give students ready-made knowledge, but points out the path to acquiring knowledge and teaches how to obtain knowledge. This is especially important when the teacher teaches Russian as a non-native language. Teaching the Russian language in modern conditions requires completely new, innovative approaches from a language teacher both to the content of the lesson and to the choice of educational technologies, effective teaching methods, and diagnosing the level of proficiency in Russian as a non-native language.

In order for students to work productively in the future and see their results, motivation is needed. In general, motivation must be present throughout the educational process. Its productivity depends on how the teacher skillfully organizes the lesson. But here we should not talk about the one-sided activity of the teacher. The teacher can achieve any positive results only in collaboration with the student. And there should always be feedback. If there is no feedback, then the student will not know about his further actions.[1.85]

Dialogue occupies a central place in the modern lesson. Dialogue in the classroom can promote intellectual development and their learning performance. Conversation is

an integral part of student learning. When we enter the classroom, we already enter into a conversation with the students. How you start the conversation determines how interesting the lesson will be. Dialogue can be carried out at all stages of the lesson. When we constantly communicate and talk, a friendly relationship appears between teacher and student. We need to move away from the assessment system where only the teacher evaluates the student.

And such an assessment may be final and not discussed. We can say that it is not always objective. To prevent this from happening, it is very important that the student sees his achievements step by step, analyzes them, and then evaluates his work. The assessment of your classmates and consultants is no less important here. When the teacher alone gives an assessment, especially if it is a final assessment, self-assessment or the assessment of classmates can always be discussed, and the student will see his “pros” and “cons”.

In order for a student to correctly evaluate his work, he needs to be given evaluation criteria. Then he will clearly imagine how he will work, what result he will achieve, and in the end what grade he will receive, what difficulties will stand in his way, the students will be motivated, they will have an interest in learning, in the subject.

During the lesson, a friendly relationship will develop between the students and the teacher, and the students will always strive to get a good grade. Of course, all this depends on how well the teacher knows pedagogical technologies and different methods of assessing student activity. At school we often use summative assessments. During testing, during tests, and when performing certain tasks, a summative assessment is given. Summative assessment is not always objective. Such assessment is included in the journal and in the student report card.

Summative assessment is used to sum up results, for classification, certification, and recording the progress of learning. And formative learning is used to make decisions that may affect the status or future of a student, teacher or school. And here motivation and feedback are very important. Here we can emphasize the positive aspects of

formative assessment: 1. Peer assessment provides the student with real help; 2. The student knows what level he is at; 3. Makes forecasts of its activities; 4. Brings “pluses” to the student’s motivation.

Formative assessment can be used in any lesson. It is intermediate. For example, thematic accounting is also a formative assessment. Students need to get used to this. Formative assessment ensures that the teacher has listened carefully to student responses. Here we give students unlimited opportunities to improve. We want the student to learn voluntarily, independently and creatively. This can be achieved by introducing active forms and methods of work into the educational process.

Thus, we can emphasize the basic principles of the modern Russian language lesson: reliance on the age-related psychological characteristics of schoolchildren; the lesson should be addressed to each student, taking into account the uniqueness and originality of each; priority of developing forms of education: not to give ready-made knowledge, but to teach how to obtain it independently, to see a problem in a linguistic phenomenon and try to solve it; variety of lesson forms, choice of the most effective teaching techniques, methods, research nature of the lesson; a clear structure of the lesson, its plot, the interconnection of all its parts; The lesson can be roughly divided into three parts: an introduction introducing students to the problem; movement of the topic, development, deepening it, allowing schoolchildren to see the multifaceted nature of any language problem; lesson summary, conclusions, correction of acquired knowledge; a variety of forms of questioning, the questioning being organically woven into the lesson and subordinate to its objectives; practicing the norms of expressive reading; bright, figurative speech of the teacher.[2.96]

Only by following these principles will students learn how to learn and, as a result, can become independent, self-motivated, enthusiastic, confident, responsible students with developed critical thinking, fluent Russian communication, and digital competence.

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